

October newsletter

This month we spotlight the work of the Edinburgh Open Research Initiative (EORI), we also have some reading and event recommendations. Lots for you to share with your local network.

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Please read on...and let us know what you think.

Spotlight on Edinburgh...

...with PhD student Emma Wilson and Senior Lecturer Will Cawthorn.

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights the work and activities of the [Edinburgh Open Research Initiative](#). (EORI) is a grassroots collective of students and staff that aim to promote awareness of and training in Open Research practices and policies, and lobby for these to be implemented and formally recognised by the University of Edinburgh.

Learn about their activities, the benefits and challenges and what they'd like to see happen through the LNL Community Project

Read more [here](#)

From the Edinburgh team - here are some activities everyone can do right now:

- If you lecture, include a slide at the end with information and links to open research activities and communication hubs at your organization.
- Encourage the good open research practice of replacing journal names with article DOIs for example in departmental newsletters. This reduces bias for/against particular journals and journal impact factors, it also promotes the use of DOIs as persistent identifiers.
- Play the 'don't ask about the journal' game. Next time a colleague tells you they just published a paper, don't ask them where. Often they really, really want to tell you. Resist. Ask about the paper content instead.

Paper recommendation

[Not just for programmers: How GitHub can accelerate collaborative and reproducible research in ecology and evolution](#)

Here's a paper for you to read, share, discuss, use as the basis of a new project. It's not just for ecologists either, it will be of interest to researchers across many disciplines. This 2023 publication reviews 12(!) ways in which researchers can use the GitHub platform to store code, manage projects, code collaboratively, conduct peer review, write a manuscript, and use automated and continuous integration to streamline analyses. Potential barriers are discussed and there are top tips for getting started in GitHub. This paper arose from a hackathon at the [Society for Open, Reliable and Transparent Ecology and Evolution](#) (SORTEE) virtual meeting in July 2021.

Thanks to Emma Wilson, University of Edinburgh for spotting and sharing it.

UKRN resources for you

UKRN have recently released 3 new primers on Open Research. These are primarily aimed at research-enabling staff working in roles that support open research, research data management and open access. Enjoy!

Working in Open Research

Research Data Management

Open Access

Image credit: Michael Schwarzenberger - Pixabay

1in5

[1in5](#) is a framework to allow the academic community to focus some of its collective brainpower on climate and biodiversity. In the UK alone, approximately $\frac{1}{2}$ million students complete an undergraduate degree every year. Nearly every one of those students will do an extended and advanced piece of work (project, dissertation, production etc) in their final year. If 1 in 5 of those students focused their work on climate / biodiversity then we would be certain to see an impact.

1in5 is gaining momentum and are starting to turn their attention to collaborative work. There are 3 strands – supporting people to do the same thing (think Many Labs), supporting people to work across disciplines and also across academic/non-academic borders, collating the outputs (think of a climate/biodiversity version of Wikipedia and data sharing).

The 1in5 team would welcome some help / guidance from the Open Science community.

If you are interested please get in touch with:

Simon Rushton RushtonSK@cardiff.ac.uk

Chris Chambers chambersc1@cardiff.ac.uk

And read more about 1in5 work [here](#)

Chat with LNLs on Gather Town

We are relaunching the UKRN Gather Town, this is a virtual space platform where you can have informal 1-2-1 or group meetings. The UKRN Gather Town space was created and is maintained by Etienne Roesch (former LNL now Institutional Lead at University of Reading). The main meeting is held at 9:30 am – 10:00 am on the first Monday of every month but the space is open all the time for you to use.

Here is the link <https://bit.ly/UKRNMONDAY>

We will also send email invites to all LNLs ahead of next month's meeting on Monday 6th November. Gather Town is an easy space to navigate, simply use the arrow keys to move around. There are open spaces where everyone can

chat, closed spaces - for example chairs around a table - for small group conversations, and an auditorium where you can broadcast from the stage. It's your space, feel free to turn up and chat with fellow LNLs on Monday 6th November or reach out to a LNL and arrange a meeting there at any time.

Open Access Week

As many of you will know, the global research community celebrates [Open Access Week](#) from the 23rd to the 29th of October.

This year the theme is [community over commercialisation](#) and encourages candid conversations which approaches to open scholarship prioritise the best interests of the public and the academic community—and which do not. #OAWeek

Open Access Week events

[Big Team Science Conference](#)

23 - 25 October, 2023

The goal of this three-day virtual conference is to bring together a multidisciplinary group of researchers, funders, and stakeholders to discuss advancements, challenges, and future opportunities related to big team science.

Fees are both reasonable and optional. Keynote speakers include:

Madalina Vlasceanu

Assistant Professor, Psychology, New York University, US; International Collaboration to Understand Climate Action.

Nokuthula Mchunu

Deputy Director, The National Research Foundation of South Africa Africa Open Science Platform.

And UKRN's very own...

Marcus Munafò

Professor of Biological Psychology and MRC Investigator, University of Bristol, UK; UK Reproducibility Project

The Conference programme is available [here](#)

[Joint Essex & Derby event](#)

23 - 27th October 2023

The University of Essex Research Services Team in the Library have co-organised a week long series of events with Library colleagues from the University of Derby. All sessions are being held online via Microsoft Teams and are open to everyone, including the public. Sessions will be recorded and shared post event.

More general information about open research hosted at the University of Essex can be found [here](#)

November event

[Oxford | Berlin Autumn School on Open and Responsible Research 2023](#)

20 -24 November 2023

Please add any open events you may be running to the [Open Research Calendar](#) and also to look for ones to attend.

Free online course

Here's a free online course for you to share with your local network members.

[Open Science: Sharing your Research with the World](#)

This MOOC run by the Delft University of Technology (TU Delft), is a 6 week

course requiring 3-4 hours a week. It will enable you to explore ways to apply Open Science principles to academic work - including your own. Learn how to share your research effectively and responsibly, building greater visibility and impact. Starts 25 October 2023

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing. Would you like to be a guest editor? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

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